

THE PRINCIPAL'S MANAGEMENT IN PREVENTING BULLYING THROUGH THE CHILD-FRIENDLY SCHOOL PROGRAM AT SMP NEGERI 6 SANGATTA UTARA

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Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the principal's management in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara. The study employed a qualitative approach with a case study design. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, observation, and documentation, involving the principal, vice principal, teachers, educational staff, students, and parents as informants. The data were analyzed using the interactive model of Miles and Huberman, which includes data collection, data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing or verification. The findings revealed that the principal's management in bullying prevention was implemented through four management functions, namely planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling or evaluating. In the planning aspect, anti-bullying policies were systematically, participatively, and integratively incorporated into official school documents. In the organizing aspect, the principal established a clear work structure involving various school stakeholders. In the implementation aspect, bullying prevention was carried out through preventive, educative, and corrective approaches, including socialization, character building, counseling services, and gradual case handling. In the controlling and evaluation aspect, the principal conducts continuous monitoring, coordination, and follow-up actions to improve program effectiveness. This study concludes that the success of bullying prevention depends not only on the existence of formal policies but also on the principal's managerial capacity to implement the Child-Friendly School Program consistently, collaboratively, humanely, and with a strong orientation toward child protection

Keywords: *principal management, bullying, Child-Friendly School, bullying prevention, educational management.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a strategic instrument in developing superior, character-based, and competitive human resources. Schools, as formal educational institutions, serve not only as a place to transfer knowledge but also as a vehicle for the formation of students' values, morals, and social skills. Therefore, schools are required to create a safe and comfortable learning environment that supports optimal student growth and development. A safe learning environment is an essential component of quality education, as the educational process focuses not only on academic achievement but also on protecting children's dignity, participation, and well-being in all aspects of school life (UNICEF, 2009). However, in practice, schools are not yet completely free from various forms of violence. One form of violence that still occurs frequently is bullying. Bullying is aggressive behavior that is intentional, repeated, and involves an imbalance of power between the perpetrator and the victim (Olweus, 1993; Rigby, 2012). In the school context, bullying can occur in physical, verbal, social, or relational forms, and also through digital media. Among these various forms, verbal bullying is often the easiest to normalize as a joke, even though it can actually leave serious psychological impacts on students. The impact of bullying cannot be underestimated. Various studies have shown that the experience of being a victim of bullying is associated with anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, decreased psychosocial adjustment, and disruption to students' learning processes (Hawker & Boulton, 2000). Therefore, bullying is not simply a matter of ordinary mischief, but a real threat to the quality of the school climate and educational success. When schools fail to provide a sense of security, education's function as a space for

developing students' potential is compromised. The phenomenon of bullying is also a global issue. UNESCO reports that nearly one-third of students worldwide have experienced bullying, and this condition impacts students' health, well-being, and educational achievement (UNESCO, 2019). These findings demonstrate that bullying is not merely an individual issue, but a systemic problem that requires a strong institutional and managerial response. In the Indonesian context, efforts to prevent violence in educational institutions have been legally based through Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 82 of 2015 concerning the Prevention and Response to Acts of Violence in Educational Institutions. This regulation emphasizes that educational institutions are obliged to protect children from acts of violence, prevent students from committing violence, and regulate systematic handling mechanisms.

In addition, the government also developed a Child-Friendly School (SRA) policy through the Regulation of the Minister of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Number 8 of 2014. This policy positions schools as spaces that must guarantee the fulfillment of children's rights, protection from violence and discrimination, and children's participation in school life. Conceptually, the child-friendly school approach is also in line with the child-friendly schools framework that emphasizes safe, inclusive, protective education, and is centered on the best interests of children (Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, 2014; UNICEF, 2009). However, the success of the Child-Friendly School Program does not depend solely on the existence of a policy document. The program's effectiveness is greatly influenced by how the principal manages, organizes, mobilizes, and oversees all school resources to ensure that child protection goals are truly realized in daily practice. From an educational management perspective, the principal holds a strategic position as a leader and manager who determines the direction of policy, organizational culture, and the effectiveness of school programs (Mulyasa, 2022). Therefore, the success of bullying prevention in schools depends heavily on the principal's managerial capacity to translate policies into consistent, concrete actions.

Theoretically, George R. Terry's management functions, which include planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling, provide a relevant framework for analyzing bullying prevention through the Child-Friendly School Program. In this context, school principals need to systematically design anti-bullying programs, clearly assign roles and responsibilities, ensure program implementation through coaching and a positive culture, and conduct ongoing monitoring and evaluation. If any of these functions are not implemented optimally, the child-friendly school policy risks stalling at the administrative level and failing to produce tangible changes in the behavior of school residents. This idea aligns with the view that effective principal leadership is crucial for the quality of school management and the success of educational organizational change (Mulyasa, 2022). In the context of SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara, bullying, particularly in the form of verbal violence, remains a real problem. Based on internal school data, approximately 35 students are recorded as victims of bullying each year. Preliminary interviews indicate that the most prevalent forms are teasing, negative nicknames, and social exclusion. Not all cases are reported because victims feel afraid, embarrassed, or worried about further consequences.

This fact indicates that verbal bullying is latent and difficult to detect, thus requiring a responsive, systematic, and sustainable managerial approach through properly implemented school policies. Previous research generally discusses bullying from the perspective of the psychological impact on victims, the effectiveness of anti-bullying programs, or the implementation of child-friendly schools in general. However, research specifically examining the principal's management based on the POAC management function in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program in the local context of junior high schools is still limited. Therefore, this study is important to conduct a comprehensive analysis of how the principal carries out the functions of planning, organizing, implementing, as well as monitoring and evaluating in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara. Academically, this research is expected to enrich the study of educational management, particularly in the application of principal management functions to child protection and bullying prevention. Practically, the results are expected to provide the basis for recommendations for principals, teachers, and policymakers in strengthening the implementation of the Child-Friendly School Program to ensure a truly safe, inclusive school environment that supports optimal student development.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study design. This approach was chosen because the study aims to understand in-depth the principal's management practices in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara. The case study design was used because the research focused on a specific location, allowing researchers to gain a comprehensive, contextual, and in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under study. The qualitative approach was used to explore the meanings,

perceptions, strategies, and experiences of participants in the real context of program implementation at the school. The research was conducted at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara, East Kutai Regency, East Kalimantan Province. The research location was selected based on the school's implementation of the Child-Friendly School Program and its concrete efforts to prevent bullying. The research took place from September 2015 to January 2016, encompassing preparation, data collection, data analysis, and report preparation.

The data sources in this study consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained directly from informants through in-depth interviews and observations. Informants were determined using a purposive sampling technique, namely selected based on their knowledge, experience, and direct involvement in the implementation of bullying prevention programs and Child-Friendly Schools. Research informants included the principal, vice principal, teachers, education staff, students, and parents. Secondary data were obtained from various relevant documents, such as the school's vision and mission, the Child-Friendly School work program, student regulations, guidance and counseling records, the school's organizational structure, and other documents supporting the research focus.

In this qualitative research, the researcher served as the primary instrument. To assist in data collection, interview guidelines, observation guidelines, and documentation tools were used. The interview guidelines were developed based on the principal's management function dimensions, which include planning, organizing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating bullying prevention through the Child-Friendly School Program. Data collection techniques were conducted through triangulation techniques, namely interviews, observation, and documentation. Interviews were conducted semi-structured to provide informants with space to explain their experiences and perspectives more broadly. Observations were conducted non-participatory in the natural setting of the school to observe the physical environment, interaction patterns among school members, the implementation of Child-Friendly School activities, and the school's response to bullying behavior. Documentation was used to complement and strengthen the data from interviews and observations through written evidence and relevant school archives.

Data analysis used the Miles and Huberman interactive model, which includes four stages: data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing or verification. In the data reduction stage, researchers select, focus, and group data according to the research focus, namely planning, organizing, implementing, and monitoring and evaluation. The reduced data is then presented in the form of a descriptive narrative to facilitate understanding of the patterns, relationships, and meanings that emerge from the field findings. The final stage is carried out through gradual conclusion drawing and continuous verification throughout the research process. Data validity was maintained through technical and source triangulation. Technical triangulation was conducted by comparing the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, while source triangulation was conducted by comparing information from various informants, such as the principal, teachers, students, education staff, and parents. This step was taken to ensure the consistency, credibility, and accuracy of data regarding the principal's management in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result

The results of the study show that the principal's management in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara has been carried out through four management functions, namely planning, organizing, implementing, and monitoring and evaluation. In terms of planning, the principal has implemented a systematic, participatory, and integrated bullying prevention plan within official school documents. This is evident in the inclusion of an anti-bullying policy in the School Work Plan (RKS), school regulations, and the Guidance and Counseling program. Planning is also carried out through participatory policy formulation, program integration into school documents, the development of a structured guidance and counseling program, strengthening a child-friendly school culture, and establishing rules and sanctions within the school regulations. These findings indicate that bullying prevention is not carried out incidentally, but rather is designed as part of the school management system. In terms of organization, the research findings indicate that the principal has established a clear working structure for bullying prevention through the Child-Friendly School Team or Violence Prevention Team. The division of tasks is carried out functionally, with the principal as the person responsible for policy, the vice principal for student affairs as the implementation coordinator, the guidance and counseling teacher as the counseling service implementer, the homeroom teacher as the supervisor and mentor in the classroom, the subject teachers as the instillers of character values, and the committee and parents as supporting partners. This

structure demonstrates cross-role coordination in addressing bullying in the school environment, although parental involvement still needs to be improved for optimal results. In terms of implementation, research results show that bullying prevention is carried out through preventive, educational, and corrective approaches. Program implementation includes anti-bullying outreach through school ceremonies and activities, integration of character values into learning, fostering discipline and tolerance, counseling and mentoring services by guidance counselors, and gradual and structured case management. This implementation demonstrates that schools focus not only on responding to cases but also on fostering a positive and child-friendly school culture.

In terms of supervision and evaluation, the research findings indicate that principals conduct supervision through monitoring of learning and student activities, direct observation, reports from homeroom teachers and guidance counselors, monitoring changes in student behavior, and coordinating internal meetings. Evaluation is conducted through team meetings, case reflections, and analysis of the causes of bullying. Evaluation results are then used to strengthen policy dissemination, improve coordination between school elements, involve parents more actively, adjust coaching strategies, and conduct further monitoring of students involved in bullying cases. Thus, supervision and evaluation do not stop at problem identification but are directed at continuous program improvement.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study confirm that school principals play a central role in bullying prevention through the implementation of management functions. In the planning function, principals have demonstrated the ability to develop strategic steps that are focused, participatory, and integrated with school policies. This aligns with Terry's view that planning is the process of setting goals and the steps necessary to achieve desired results (Terry, 1971). In the educational context, good planning not only supports improving school quality but also protects students through systematic and sustainable policies (Mulyasa, 2022). The findings of this study also indicate that anti-bullying policies in schools have been directed towards a systemic approach, rather than simply a short-term response to incidents. This condition aligns with the whole-school or whole-education approach, which emphasizes that bullying prevention must be built through school policies, a positive culture, and the involvement of all school elements (UNESCO, 2019).

In the organizing function, the principal has implemented a clear division of tasks and responsibilities among the elements involved. This finding shows that bullying prevention is not solely the responsibility of the guidance and counseling teacher, but is a shared responsibility of the entire school community. This aligns with the concept of organization in management, which emphasizes the importance of clear structures, division of authority, coordination, and collaboration to effectively achieve organizational goals (Terry, 1971). From an educational leadership perspective, the principal's steps demonstrate the role of school leaders in mobilizing human resources collaboratively to build a safe and conducive school culture (Mulyasa, 2022). The involvement of parents and the school committee as supporting partners is also relevant to Bronfenbrenner's developmental ecology theory, which positions the family as a vital part of the environment influencing child development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). However, this study also indicates that synergy between schools and parents still needs to be strengthened for bullying prevention to be more effective.

In terms of implementation, the research findings show that the bullying prevention program is implemented through preventive, educational, and corrective approaches. The preventive approach is evident in socialization and character development, the educational approach is evident in the integration of anti-bullying values into learning, while the corrective approach is evident in counseling services and gradual case handling. These findings align with Lickona's character education theory, which emphasizes the importance of habituation, role models, and ongoing development in shaping students' moral behavior (Lickona, 1991/2012). Furthermore, the program's implementation also reflects the principles of Child-Friendly Schools, which prioritize the best interests of children, the fulfillment of children's rights, and protection from violence in the educational process (Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection [KPPPA], 2014; UNICEF, 2009). Schools do not prioritize repressive punishment as the primary strategy, but rather emphasize development, mentoring, and behavioral change. This approach also aligns with Olweus's view that handling bullying must include protection for victims and development for perpetrators in a balanced manner (Olweus, 1993).

In the supervision and evaluation function, the principal systematically monitored program implementation and student behavior dynamics. Supervision was conducted through various channels, ranging from direct observation and teacher reports to internal meetings. These findings indicate that controlling in school management is not solely carried out to find errors, but to ensure that program implementation continues according to planned objectives (Terry, 1971). In the educational context, effective supervision is also part of the principal's leadership in

maintaining the quality of school processes and climate on an ongoing basis (Mulyasa, 2022). Evaluations conducted through case reflections and team meetings demonstrate an orientation toward continuous improvement. This aligns with the concept of formative evaluation, which positions evaluation as the basis for continuous program improvement (Stufflebeam, 2003). Thus, the supervision and evaluation function in this study serves not only as a control tool but also as an organizational learning mechanism to strengthen the effectiveness of the Child-Friendly School Program.

Overall, the results of this study indicate that the principal's management in preventing bullying behavior at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara has been quite successful and reflects the implementation of the POAC management function as a whole. Planning is carried out systematically, organization is built through collaboration across school elements, implementation is carried out in a humanistic and educational manner, and monitoring and evaluation are directed towards continuous program improvement (Terry, 1971; Mulyasa, 2022). These findings reinforce the view that the success of bullying prevention is not solely determined by the existence of formal policies, but is highly dependent on the principal's capacity to manage the program consistently, collaboratively, and oriented towards child protection (UNESCO, 2019; KPPPA, 2014).

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the principal's management in preventing bullying behavior through the Child-Friendly School Program at SMP Negeri 6 Sangatta Utara has been implemented comprehensively through the functions of planning, organizing, implementing, as well as monitoring and evaluation. In the planning aspect, the principal has formulated an anti-bullying policy systematically, structured, and participatory by integrating it into the School Work Plan, regulations, and Guidance and Counseling program. In the organizational aspect, the division of tasks and responsibilities between school elements has been carried out clearly, thus supporting the collaborative implementation of the program. In the implementation aspect, bullying prevention is carried out through a preventive, educational, and corrective approach that emphasizes character building, mentoring, and protection for students. Meanwhile, in the supervision and evaluation aspect, the principal has conducted regular monitoring and follow-up as part of an effort to continuously improve the program. Overall, these findings indicate that the success of bullying prevention is not only determined by the existence of formal policies, but also by the principal's capacity to manage the program consistently, humanely, and oriented towards child protection.

Based on these findings, schools need to continue strengthening a child-friendly school culture by internalizing the values of mutual respect, empathy, discipline, and tolerance in all educational activities. Principals are expected to further optimize cross-school coordination, strengthen program supervision, and increase the involvement of parents and school committees to ensure more effective synergy between schools and families. Teachers are also expected to continue instilling character values in learning and increasing sensitivity to early signs of bullying behavior. Furthermore, further research is recommended to expand the scope of locations, use a quantitative or mixed methods approach, and examine external factors such as the influence of social media to gain a more comprehensive understanding of bullying prevention in the school environment.

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